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MOLECULAR BASIS FOR THE RESISTANCE TO VARROA
IN APIS MELLIFERA

Base molecolare per la resistenza alla Varroa in Apis mellifera

The ectoparasitic mite *Varroa destructor* is considered the most significant pathological threat to the western honey bee *Apis mellifera*, as it leads to the death of most colonies if left untreated. An alternative approach to chemical treatments is to selectively enhance heritable honey bee traits of resistance or tolerance to the mite through breeding programs, or select for naturally surviving untreated colonies.

Through a literature review of studies documenting traits of *A. mellifera* populations either selectively bred or naturally selected for resistance and tolerance to mite parasitism, we investigated the genetic bases of the different phenotypes allowing survival to varroa. Comparing 'omics studies (genomics, transcriptomics, and proteomics) of *A. mellifera* resistance and tolerance to the parasite provides a detailed overview of the current state of the research projects and breeding efforts against varroa.

The most striking result is the lack of overlap in the findings across studies: the same regions of the genome to be involved have been rarely reported, independently from investigation of the same resistance/tolerance trait or not. Although there is a poor overlap of specific molecular markers between studies, the functions associated with such genetic markers and enriched in the different studies show some consistency between the different populations phenotyped. Notably, functions related neural sensitivity, signal transmission, sensory perception, olfaction, transporter activity, metabolic process and oxidative phosphorylation have been found in several studies looking at varroa sensitive hygiene (VSH) and hygienic behaviour (HYG).

The resistance and tolerance mechanisms of honey bees that survive with varroa, whether acquired through natural selection or through selective breeding efforts, span a tremendous range of honey bee behaviour, individual immunity, population dynamics, and relationships with associated pathogens. It is very likely that these mechanisms do not operate alone but function in combination. The importance of specific adaptations may also vary across environments. Future research should aim at understanding the potential links between traits, and why so little overlap is found in studies looking at molecular pathways underlying varroa resistance and tolerance. Such efforts will also help develop practical tools to assist selection programs to enhance varroa resistance and tolerance, either by offering molecular markers or by finding proxies of complex traits that could help with phenotyping colonies in the field. Phenotyping efforts and molecular marker development are complimentary approaches, and efficient development of marker assisted selection relies on the development of effective and reliable phenotyping tools.

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